

Through parents' eyes: Exploring parental involvement's experiences on online learning

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 1, 2022

Revised Feb 11, 2023

Accepted Mar 2, 2023

Keywords:

Online learning

Parental involvement

Primary school

Socio cultural theory

Thematic content analysis

ABSTRACT

The engagement of parents in their children's education has been the subject of several studies for decades, but socio-cultural theories that highlight parents' mentoring of their children's social learning have received less attention. This semi structure interview study intended to explore parents' experiences of their involvement on children online learning. The study was conducted to obtain the data from six parents whose children attended primary schools. The data garnered from online and offline interviewing were transcribed and then interpreted by employing thematic content analysis. The study revealed four themes including parents' emotional state and parental burnout, technological awareness, pedagogical experiences and benefits of online learning from parents' perspectives. This study underlines the value of parental cooperation in fostering children's learning and lowering mothers' stress levels, particularly in online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The switch to distance learning is becoming a top choice for students of all ages across the world as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown, which has caused global disruption to education and lengthy school closures. Over 1.75 billion pupils' learning activities have been impeded in over 200 countries that have enacted complete or partial lockdown around the world as of April 14, 2020 [1]. In fact, schools were closed in practically every country in the world in March 2020, including Germany, Austria, Switzerland [2], Spain [3], and Indonesia [4]. Teachers, children, and parents are all put in a new predicament when a school is locked down [2].

E-teaching and e-learning have evolved as complimentary options that aid in the smooth running of educational activities [1]. However, the government's policy of adopting remote learning to replace traditional learning in order to halt the pandemic's spread has its own set of concern and problems [5]. In the United Kingdom, for instance, the mental health impact on children aged 5 to 16 years has increased from 10.8% in 2017 to 16% in July 2020 [6]. Singh *et al.* [7] also discussed the stress that children and adolescents encounter. Due to uncertain financial conditions, school closures, and suspension of educational services for their children, parents have psychological suffering and collateral anxiety [8]. Another study's findings shed light on the enormous stress that parents in Ireland cope with when it comes to supporting schooling at home (SAH) [9]. For decades, considerable research literature has shown the effectiveness of parental involvement, which facilitates students' academic attainment for pupils of all ages [10]–[12].

In recent years, there has been a rise in study on parental involvement [13]. For instance, four conclusions were presented in Wilder's meta-analysis [14]: i) The results revealed a positive relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement; ii) Regarding parents' expectations for their children's academic success, the link was strongest; iii) The impact of parental involvement on students' academic achievement was the smallest when it was measured as homework assistance; and iv) Across grade levels and ethnic groupings, there was a consistent relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement. In addition, a multitude of studies have shown that parental involvement has a substantial impact on children's educational process, academic learning, and outcomes [15]–[21] and long-term school performance [22].

Although it is generally recognized and highly indicated that parents' help at home can significantly improve children's learning [23], [24], and the children's development of social and intellectual foundation [25], the COVID-19 pandemic highlights the importance of parental involvement [26]. In the latest research, the parents encounter impediments and lack knowledge and expertise in assisting children's remote learning during this pandemic [26]. It is not an easy transition for everyone, particularly for children to change from traditional learning to remote learning. Thus, the role of parents is inevitable and becomes the most influential factor. Research has shown the value of parental involvement particularly in primary grades, which is a direct predictor of grades in middle and high school [17]. Considering the effects of parental involvement on students' academic achievement, and school performance, this study is a great importance of showing parents' emotional state and their interactions with children's learning and pedagogical experiences during coronavirus from the perspective of social cultural theory. Furthermore, although there has been a lot of studies on parental participation, little of it has been examined through the lens of social and cultural theory. Based on the identified research gap and the objectives of the study, we pose the questions as: i) How are parents' emotional state and parental burnout depicted in supporting their children online learning?; ii) What pedagogical experiences do the parents encounter during online learning?; iii) How do the parents struggle for technology?; and iv) How does online learning benefit the parents?

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

This qualitative study relied on semi-structured in-depth interviews with six mothers of elementary school children in Jakarta and Depok area, Indonesia. The semi-structured interviews allows for open-ended questions to garner more genuine and in-depth data [27]. Such interviews allow researchers to explore participants' experiences, activities, and beliefs in their own language [28]. This study was conducted in 2021-2022 to elaborate the parents' experiences during their assistance and supports to help their children in learning process at home. Thus, we followed the social culture theory by Vygotsky [29], [30], which emphasized parents as mentors who support their children's learning social development.

2.2. Participants

Six participants are mothers whose ages range from 29 to 47 years old residing in urban cities of Indonesia. The participants were recruited after taking part in the online workshop about parenting on April 16, 2020, which is a part of our community service activity. So, we used purposive sampling technique since we recruited and selected participants based on three criteria: i) parents whose children are primary school students, ii) their eagerness to share information about their feelings while supporting their children and their teaching experiences during the pandemic, and iii) for those participants who are not in teaching profession inasmuch as our research focuses on primary school settings. We did not include the teacher participants as we assumed that they have no specific problems teaching the children. We invited all to join the Zoom meeting, but 10 responded our invitation, it is probably due to our previous information about the criteria. However, in the following zoom meeting, only six took part the research. They voluntarily participated in the research after we explained the purpose of the research. To respect their privacy, all names are pseudonyms. So that the participants' confidentiality and anonymity would be strictly sustained. Table 1 shows the demographic data of participants.

Table 1. Socio demographic data of participants

Name	Age	Level of education	The children ages and gender	Employment
Dewi	37	Undergraduate	Zoni aged 9 (male); Shakira aged 7, Olif aged 5 (female)	An office worker
Anti	30	Senior high school graduate	Nirma aged 10; Nit & Nat (twin), aged 7 (female)	Self employed
Vita	32	Undergraduate	Aliva aged 9 (female); one male aged 7	A house wife
Diva	29	Undergraduate	Maria aged 9 (female)	A house wife
Dyana	47	Undergraduate	Kristin aged 13 (female), one male aged 8	An entrepreneur
Silia	35	Undergraduate	Adam aged 10, Adi aged 7 (male); Aldina aged 5 (female)	An office worker

2.3. Data collection

All the data collection relied on interviews, which were conducted online and offline. The first interview was conducted once through Zoom meeting to inform about the objectives of the research, and its procedures. In addition, we also questioned general information about the participants' professions, ages, educational background, the number of children they have and their perspectives on online learning and their states of mind during the ongoing pandemic for about two hours. The following face to face interviews were conducted with previous appointment several times with different participants. Each interview lasted for about an hour in different places based on our agreement. The interviews were recorded and transcribed, and then analyzed using thematic content analysis. Moreover, we also obtained the data via WhatsApp since two of the participants could not meet face to face. The questions are related to their perspectives about online learning, the obstacles they face, their experiences assisting their children in learning process, the benefits of online learning and how they handle the problems related to the tasks, and technological devices. Since all of participants attended our online workshop, we did not encounter problems in approaching them. Thus, they did not hesitate to explore their point of views and answered our questions. In qualitative research, the emotional and personal bond between researchers and participants are needed as to make participants feel relaxed and enjoyable during the study. This close bonding leads participants to explore voluntarily their experiences and perspectives, particularly on the researched topic.

2.4. Data analysis

Before we analyzed the interview data, we sent our transcribes to participants to do member checking for data trustworthiness and to keep research ethics in data reconstruction [31]. For data analysis, we used thematic content analysis to find the underlying meaning in the text [32]. When looking for patterns and themes in people's experiences, thematic content analysis is employed methodically. This thematic method seeks to comprehend "what is being conveyed," rather than the story's structure, and to identify problems and experiences based on predetermined themes [33]. We followed the procedures of the data analysis by Widodo [34]. The analysis focuses on reading the interview transcripts multiple times to comprehend the meaning and discourse of the story, and then the transcripts are coded according to the themes, and subthemes, that are likely to emerge. After coding, we classified the important data, and interpreted the data. The last stage, we gave a change to participants to give feedback on our interpretations. We identified four main themes including parents' emotional state and burnout, technological awareness, pedagogical experience and teaching benefits during online learning. Table 2 shows the illustrations of thematic data analysis techniques.

Table 2. Illustrations of thematic data analysis techniques

Interview data	Data encoding	Theme
Silia#1	I do not think teaching the children is difficult but what make me tired (burnout) and annoyed (emotion) is having to record the learning process and send it to the teacher (support the children).	Emotional state and parental burnout
Anti#5	I am not a kind of gadget addict. I use mobile phone only for communication. However, now I learn a lot from my smartphone (learning experience). Well, I feel that the existence of technology (technological awareness) really helps the children during online learning, particularly the invention of Zoom meeting.	Technological awareness
Dyana#2	I read all the books, browse the internet, and watch YouTube (effort to support the children learning) how to explain the lesson with fun ways in order that my children will not get bored. They feel so happy (positive feeling) because I use game to explain the lesson (pedagogical experience)	Pedagogical experience
Dewi#3	I think I can master the subject matter more (advantages to support the child), because like it or not, we should read and study the book before teaching our children (preparation before teaching), right?	Teaching benefits of online learning

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Parents' emotional state and parental burnout

The spread of COVID-19 in Indonesia resulted in a variety of emotional and exhausting stories from all people including research participants of six mothers who assisted their primary school-aged children. Because helping their children online learning is their first experience, each of individual must encounter and overcome a variety of difficulties, hurdles, and challenges. For example, Anti, a self-employed mother with three children. She must divide her work and assist her three-elementary school-aged children. She is fortunate, though, because her husband shares responsibilities and she also has a sister in law who assists her in teaching English for her children. She shares her feeling how she handles the problem as following account.

“What else can I do! I must be able to overcome this problem. I'm tired, because I also have to make cakes to sell and send them to shops, stalls or markets. At night I have to prepare all the ingredients and, in the morning, I make the cake, so I usually get up at 3 or 4 o'clock. At 7 o'clock I usually check the messages one by one in the WhatsApp group. I have 3 children, and all of them are still in elementary school. I share the responsibilities with my husband. He is the one who prepares all the learning equipment, books, desks, stationary and I am the one who check what the children have to do and help the assignments given by the teacher. Even on Sundays, I need to submit the assignment on physical education. Sigh... hmm, we have to videotape her sports activity by wearing sports uniform. For the first two semesters, I was initially exhausted, upset with the situation but because it has been going on for almost two years, it gradually becomes a new habit.” (Anti, face-to-face interview)

Divya, a young housewife with one child in first grade, shares a similar condition and feeling. She realizes that teaching is a difficult occupation and she gains deeper respect for the field after schooling her own child. When I ask her how she feels about teaching her child during the online learning, she is somewhat emotional and expressive. Here is her following response.

“Stress, stress and stress, that's what I feel. Angry, upset, annoying with the situation. All feelings are mixed up. But for the sake of my child, I must be able to help do her works. If sometimes I don't understand the answer, I ask one of my family members who also happens to be a teacher. But this condition makes me understand more about the condition of the teacher, it turns out that being a teacher is not easy, you have to be patient, persistent. So, if a teacher pinches a child, maybe she/he can't contain his emotions anymore. If my child still doesn't understand what I teach, I will scold her (with smirking face). When you are tired and you have to teach the child and the child still doesn't understand, you know what I mean, right! With this situation, frankly, I feel the difficulty of being a teacher and it makes me respect teachers more.” (Divya, face-to-face interview)

Dyana, an entrepreneur woman with two children, is a positive person who perceives the online learning as an opportunity for her to learn and read books again to recall her memory. She finds it teaching not as difficult as she imagined beforehand. It is fun and enjoyable after she knows how to do it, as her following experiences.

“At first, I was confused about what to do and didn't know how to teach my children, but as time went on, I read and studied books again. Well, we can't just complain about the conditions that are happening all over the world. We have to find a solution. After I studied books again and it made me better at teaching my children. I have two children, one is an elementary school student in the fifth grade, and the other one is a junior high school student who doesn't really need my help. So, teaching is actually not really difficult, it is fun if you really feel enjoyable. And I have more quality time with my family now because of the pandemic. I used to travel a lot due to my work.” (Dyana, WhatsApp interview)

Support from a partner is crucial for persons who are married to minimize burdens, share obligations, and build positive attitude. Silia, an office worker, is experiencing this because her spouse is unable to assist her due to his work in medical service. This situation has an emotional impact on her mentality because she has to handle everything by herself.

“Yes, it is tiring, especially for me, who has to divide my work and teach the children. My husband keeps working and can't help. He works in public health center. I have three children, two are in elementary grade 1 and grade 3 and one is in kindergarten. I don't think teaching the children is difficult but what make me tired and annoyed is having to record the learning process and send it to the teacher. Every day there must be assignments, and I must take photos of the assignments as well. It's so disturbing. Nevertheless, I have to keep myself positive with this situation since it will help my children's learning and their attainment.” (Silia, WhatsApp interview)

The emotional feelings expressed by the other mothers differ slightly from those expressed by Vita, a 32-year-old housewife who believes that the pandemic has brought her closer to her children and has made her more patient and more knowledgeable because she can learn from her children's books and teacher's explanation during the Zoom meeting.

“I reckon there is a fun side, because we can be creative with children. There is a sense of enthusiasm and pleasure when listening to what children learn. But there is a tiring side when we have to share time with other activities at the same time, and it makes me dizzy sometimes. Mothers are becoming smarter and more patient as their bonds with their children grow stronger. Hahaha (laughing).” (Vita, face to face interview).

Someone’s personality also affects how she/he handles the situation. Dewi is a kind of easy going person who works for a travel agency. During the pandemic, her boss still requested her to work since she is in charge in finance department, but in a flexible hour. She informs us about her feeling on supporting her children learning.

“For me, actually, there is no big different before and after pandemic related to teaching my children. I am accustomed to teaching them since all my children need my guidance. But during the pandemic I have to become like “a 24-hour teacher”, I have to prepare all the things, check WhatsApp group, explain the task to my children, and check their tasks before sending them to the teacher. It’s somewhat bothering, though. It’s still ok for me because it’s my responsibility as a parent. But the problem is that my boss cut 25% of my salary for a few months and then 50% for following months that makes me upset.”

3.2. Pedagogical experiences

One of new things facing the students’ parents during online learning is teaching experience. This new experience is uttered by a mother with two children.

“Yes, whether I like it or not, I need to study again, for example, during Arabic course that I do not really comprehend, ha ha ha (laughing). I also learned to be patient as it became clear that teaching children was not what we desired. It can be quick at times, but the child may not want it or require a different approach. As parents, we must learn that each child’s learning style is unique and different. My two children have very different learning styles. My first child likes to learn while doing other things, such as singing or eating, and she must be accompanied until she finished doing the task as well. She is a quick learner and able to grasp what I teach rapidly. But with the other one, I have to explain several times, sometimes she seems daydreaming, and it took her a long time to react or respond the lesson.” (Vita, face to face interview)

Watching YouTube and browsing the internet about the lesson and how to teach the children with interesting ways also help parents to support their pedagogical experience.

“One thing that I feel grateful due to the pandemic is that I think I have a hidden talent. Teaching is my hidden talent. I read all the books, browse the internet, and watch YouTube how to explain the lesson with fun ways in order that my children will not get bored. They feel so happy because I use game to explain the lesson. I think I also become more patient.” (Dyana, WhatsApp interview)

Anti, as a self-employed, faces similar experience that makes her realize that teaching children on online learning is not as easy as she imagines.

“I usually help my children do their homework. But helping children on online learning is a different thing. I need to make sure that all my children understand the instructions given by the teachers. Even sometimes, I get upset with the teachers who just give homework without explanation or just send the video. So, I have to explain again all the things to my children and make sure that they have done all homework. Before that, I learn it by myself and browse the internet to find the answers. I also share with my friends who have teaching profession. I think they help me a lot.” (Anti, face to face interview)

As a housewife, Diva almost never helps her child’s learning due to her inability to explain the lesson. Fortunately, her husband has more patience and ability to teach their children. However, the online learning makes her attempt to support the child’s learning as she shares her story.

“I don’t think I am good at explaining the lesson. But this situation makes me learn how to teach and explain the things in a very easy way. I share my situation with some of my friends who happen to be teachers. They inform me some YouTube channel so I can learn a lot from it. Since my child is in the third grade, she needs my support and loves games. For example, I teach her to

memorize some new English vocabulary by using games, which I learn from YouTube. I am good at English but not Math. For Math, I let my husband teach her, since his Math is better. So, we share our responsibility in teaching and supporting our children learning." (Diva, face to face interview)

3.3. Technological awareness

The use of technology such as Zoom platform or Google Meet is inevitable on an online learning. All people need to adjust with the use of technology to accommodate an online learning. We all become "sudden technology literate" as some example interviews.

"I think almost all parents are confused by this condition, but this makes us more able and understand. For example, I have learned to use several application and software to help my children do the task well. I know how to use platforms like Zoom and Google Meeting. I also know how to record, edit the recording, and upload it to YouTube." (Dewi, face to face interview)

"Due to the pandemic, I learn how to use zoom platform, which is something new for all of us. I am not a kind of gadget addict. I use mobile phone only for communication. However, now I learn a lot from my smartphone. Well, I feel that the existence of technology really helps the children during online learning, particularly the invention of Zoom meeting." (Anti, face to face interview)

"Not only we are now familiar with Zoom, Webex or Google Meet, but we also become familiar with google classroom, google form, quizizz and some other application or software that I even do not remember. But one thing that make me realize is the importance of technology to accommodate online learning. You can imagine if there is no zoom platform, how the children, students can learn easily." (Diva, face to face interview)

"I think because of pandemic, we become familiar with some platforms such as Zoom. Since I work from home, I am accustomed to using digital technology to send the assignment to my boss. Hence, I don't think I have any big problems related with technology. One thing that I feel so grateful is that I am a fast learner and love exploring the technology so that I learn it quickly. Additionally, I can teach my children more easily as well with the help of technology. Now they know how to start the zoom meeting and do the test by using google form without my guidance anymore." (Silia, face to face interview)

3.4. Benefits of supporting children's online learning from mothers' perspectives

For students to enhance their learning and succeed in school, parental support of their children's learning has become crucial. Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, parents' roles have become more important in terms of distant learning, as elementary school-aged children require greater help and direction. In the interviews that follow, we explore the parents' viewpoints on the advantages of encouraging their children's online learning.

"Frankly speaking, the benefits of this learning condition are quite a lot for me, I understand more about technology, I become more patient, painstaking and I think I can become a teacher. I'm a graduate majoring in economics, so it's not difficult to teach, especially those related to mathematics, although there are also things that I don't know the answer to other subjects. What other benefits? I think I can master the subject matter more, because like it or not, we should read and study the book before teaching our children, right?" (Dewi, face to face interview)

Silia has a different perspective when asked about the benefits of helping her children's online learning, which brings her positive and negative aspects.

"For me, this pandemic brings me good and bad things. The bad things are our movement is limited, especially the first year. We could not go anywhere. I must divide between my works and my children's learning. I could only focus on my children's learning, helping them doing tasks and homework. It does not mean I don't like it. But in fact, preparing many things at the same time is somewhat confusing. My husband also has to work at home. Hence, we decided to make a schedule for helping the children. The good things are I have more quality time with my children and my husband too, my children also become more open about their feeling, I know more each of my children's lacks in subjects." (Silia, WhatsApp interview)

Parents expect their children to grow up to be more self-reliant and responsible. Children affected by the epidemic tend to have more positive attitudes and character, as seen by the experiences of the next two participants.

“After more than one year, I feel that my children become more responsible and independent compared before online learning. Even though I often check their homework and make sure that they really understand the task given by the teachers. They are now accustomed to starting preparing everything before the class begins. Maybe because we are not in a rush anymore. I used to prepare everything, their bags, books, uniforms, and meal for their school lunch. But now I am more relaxed.” (Anti, face to face interview)

“What I like because of pandemic is my children’s positive habit. They help one another. My first child, Amelia, sometimes helps her sister do homework, and explains something if for example, I have to do other things. On the other side, her sister, Mita helps her videotape her school activity.” (Vita, face to face interview)

The main objective of this study is to report the parents’ role and their involvement in supporting their children online learning during two years’ pandemic era, which results four themes including parents’ emotional state and burnout; pedagogical experiences, technological awareness, and the benefits of supporting children online learning in the eyes of parents’ perspectives. Pandemic condition which forces educational sector must close the schools brings emotional state of parents. Scherer [35] defined the term “emotions” refers to a broad category of phenomena, including subjective feelings, motivational tendencies, cognitions, physiological processes, and dramatic behavior of the people. Diva, Anti, and Silia experienced the feeling of upset, angry, stress, and tired with the situation while Silia and Vita had mixed feeling between positive and negative side of supporting their children online learning.

Similarly, Price, Peersman, and Matherne [36] revealed the experiences of five parents, who feel frustrated and confused with the reality in terms of technology, new learning system, and abundant of assignments which the parents do not understand. They also emphasized the importance of communication between parents, and school district personnel to solve the problems in line with the support of the children’s learning. Crea and Francis [37] elucidated that personality differences influence how emotionally people respond to a problem. This is portrayed by six participants in this research. For example, Dewi, Vita, Anti and Dyana are more positive persons who see assisting their children online learning as their responsibility and they face it with more relaxed ways whereas Diva and Silia are the ones who get stressed easily and find it difficult to adjust with the new situation.

Grzywacz and Carlson’s study [38] looked at the difficulties families encounter when trying to manage the demands of job and family life. Because it may have an impact on the kind of activities chosen, the question of finding a balance among everyday activities is crucial. One of the reasons that the researched participants feel stressed out is they have to manage their works and their responsibilities at the same time as well. In addition, support from partners is also needed to lower their stress. The availability of father is really an influential factor not only for mothers but also to their children. Research found that children who had more focused parental assistance during the lockout exhibit more favorable developmental skills [39] and greater parental involvement in their children’s academic lives and a more formal, structured approach resulted in greater academic success [40]. Furthermore, the emotional state of a child’s parents has a significant impact on how they respond emotionally during stressful situations [41]. Correspondingly, emotions associated with learning can have an impact on cognition, motivation, and achievement [40].

In terms of pedagogical experiences, Bubb and Jones [42] revealed that the pandemic has given parents a greater understanding of their children’s learning since they actively involve them in the educational process. Additionally, due to lower teachers’ support for students during the lockdown, it indicates a greater quantity of parental involvement [39]. All participants encounter new teaching experiences and have more understanding about the teaching profession. For example, Vita finds that her children have different learning styles which make her realize that the way she treats her children must be different. Diva, Anti, and Dyana have also gone through the same thing, studying books, surfing the web, and watching YouTube are some strategies in order to be able to teach their children in a simple and enjoyable manner. They also become more patient in facing their children learning difficulties. Children will do better as a result of parents’ involvement in their learning and parents’ firsthand experience. It is similar to several findings that due to their poor reading comprehension, self-monitoring abilities, competency, and increased vulnerability to the risks associated with the use of digital media, children are found to be very dependent on their parents’ and instructors’ guidance and assistance during their academic endeavors [43]–[45].

The study’s findings reveal that one of the most crucial factors in the effectiveness of online learning is the availability of supporting technologies [46]. All the research participants who live in urban cities are somewhat familiar with the smartphones, and laptop. However, the needs of new technology to

accommodate the online learning such as Zoom platform, Webex and Google Meet are something new that are experienced by all people around the world. With the help of their parents, the children are now familiar using such new platforms and applications. Bubb and Jones [42] indicated that remote teaching and learning at home helped both students and teachers become more adept at using technology. The current research findings show that the children developed their independence and willingness to assume more accountability for their own routines and learning while homes schooling. This is comparable to what the parents' assertion that their ability to educate their children technology will help them develop their own technological literacy. As a result, technology literacy and awareness play a crucial part in allowing online learning.

The final finding concerns the parents' perceptions of the advantages of online learning. For instance, children develop in maturity, openness toward their parents, helpfulness, and independence. For parents, this translates into more patience, understanding of the teaching profession, their children's strengths and shortcomings, and increased subject matter and technological literacy. The most crucial factor above all else is that parents spend more time with their family in a positive emotional environment. This current finding is related to the research finding conducted in China, particularly on the children affectionate.

Yang *et al.* [47] found that higher degrees of parental involvement are linked to higher levels of student affective engagement. In Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, how well people learn is greatly influenced by the social and relational context of their learning. During the pandemic, children do socialization with their siblings as well as they learn and support each other to accomplish their school assignments with their parents supports and mentoring. Cherry [48] noted that the sociocultural approach emphasizes how important mentors are in influencing who we become. Thus, the parents' mentoring gives a profound contribution to the children's achievement and learning development. Vygotsky's theory also emphasized the significance of play in learning [49] to develop their cognitive growth [50] and education [51]. In line with this theory, parents attempt to use a various way to teach their children with fun ways, one of which is through games to promote their understanding of learning and development of abstract thought, particularly in young ages.

4. CONCLUSION

Research on parental involvement during the COVID-19 pandemic have highlighted particular challenges for parents and children of primary schools. The period of online learning during the pandemic was a distinctive episode for children and their parents, particularly in developing countries, such as Indonesia, which have almost never experienced online learning before. The current findings have revealed the emotional state and parental burnout due to a two-year pandemic, which need both parents' engagement and parental cooperation in supporting the children online learning. In addition, high responsibility and motivation of parents to learn the subject matters by browsing the internet, watching YouTube and attempting creative ways for the sake of their children is also an influential factor of the success story facing the online learning issues. Parents' technological literacy is another essential factor to contribute the effectiveness of online learning. The last but not the least is the benefits of supporting the children online learning during the lockdown including the change of more positive vibes of parents' attitudes, and children's positive habits.

This study has some limitations including the number of participants which only six mothers of primary school children. In consequence, the findings might not represent the voices of parents. The second limitation is that the study merely focuses on the voices and experiences of parents. Thus, the further study which include the children's perspectives and experiences and teachers' supports is highly recommended in all level of education such as junior and senior high school students.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors appreciate the financial support from the Scientific Publication Support and Enhancement Unit (UPPI) and Lemlitbang, University of Muhammadiyah Prof. DR. HAMKA, with the grant number is 840 /F.03/07/2022.

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